

Multidisciplinary Surgical Research Annals

<https://msra.online/index.php/Journal/about>

Volume 3, Issue 5 (2025)

Salivary miRNA-155 As A Non-Invasive Biomarker For Periodontitis: Diagnostic, Public Health And Translational Perspectives: A Systematic Review

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

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Background: Periodontitis is a prevalent chronic inflammatory disease, with significant public health implications, Conventional diagnostic methods primarily reflect past tissue destruction and may not adequately capture active disease. saliva –based biomarkers, particularly microRNAs, have emerged as promising non –invasive tools for early diagnosis. MicroRNA-155 (miR-155) is a key regulator of inflammatory pathways and has been increasingly investigated in periodontal diseases.

Objectives: This systematic review aimed to evaluate the diagnostic potential, public health relevance, and translational applicability of salivary miR-155 as a non –invasive biomarkers for periodontitis

Methods: A systematic review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA guidelines. Electronic database including PubMed, Scopus and Google Scholar were searched for studies published between 2011 and 2025. Eligible studies assessed salivary miR-155 expression in periodontitis patients compared with healthy controls study selection, data extraction, and risk of bias assessment using the QUADAS 2 tool were performed independently by two reviewers.

Result: Included studies consistently demonstrated significantly elevated salivary miR-155 levels in periodontitis patients. Diagnostic accuracy analyses reported moderate to high sensitivity and acceptable specificity, with favorable area under the ROC curve values. Several studies also showed positive correlation between miR-155 expression and clinical periodontal parameters, suggesting an association with disease severity. Overall risk of bias was low to moderate across studies.

Conclusion: Salivary miR-155 shows strong potential as a non-invasive diagnostic biomarker for periodontitis, with implications for early detection, population screening, and precision dentistry. However, heterogeneity in methodologies highlights the need for standardized protocols and large-scale validation studies before routine clinical implementation.

INTRODUCTION:

Periodontitis is a common chronic inflammatory disease affecting the supporting tissues of the teeth and is a significant global public health burden due to its high prevalence, progressive tissue destruction, and correlation with systemic disease including cardiovascular disease and diabetes.⁽¹⁾ Traditional diagnosis of periodontitis relies largely on clinical and radiographic parameters e.g., probing depth, clinical attachment loss, bleeding on probing, which frequently identify sickness solely subsequent to significant tissue damage has transpired, limiting the potential for early intervention.^(2, 3) **Early diagnosis remains challenging because conventional clinical parameters primarily reflect historical tissue damage rather than ongoing disease activity⁽⁴⁾**

Saliva has emerged as a promising diagnostic fluid because its collection is non-invasive, simple and acceptable to patients. Salivary diagnostics can reflect both local oral and systemic pathological changes, offering potential for early detection monitoring disease activity and post treatment surveillance.^(5, 6) Among various candidates analytes in saliva such as protein, enzymes, cytokines or microbial products small non coding RNAs, notably microRNAs (miRNAs), are gaining attention due to their stability in body fluids, disease-specific expression patterns and regulatory roles in inflammation and tissue homeostasis.⁽⁷⁾ **Consequently, there is growing interest in identifying molecular biomarkers capable of detecting active periodontal inflammation at an early stage⁽⁸⁾. Saliva has gained increasing attention as a diagnostic medium due to its non-invasive collection, patient acceptability and suitability for large-scale screening⁽⁹⁾**

One miRNA in particular, miRNA-155, is a well-known regulator of immune and inflammatory responses, including modulation of cytokine production, macrophage activation, and Toll-like receptor pathways.⁽¹⁰⁾ aberrant miRNA-15 expression has been implicated in various inflammatory and immune-mediated diseases. In periodontal disease, dysregulation of miR-155 may reflect biologically plausible biomarkers for periodontitis^(7, 11)

Recent pilot and observational studies have examined salivary miR-155 as a potential non-invasive biomarker for periodontitis. For example, a study reported significantly higher salivary miR-155 levels in periodontitis patients compared to healthy controls. With a receiving operating characteristics (ROC) area under the curve (AUC) of 0.887, sensitivity of 97.1% and specificity of 78%⁽¹²⁾. Another study, including diabetic and non-diabetic subjects, identified miR-155 (alongside miR-146/b and miR-203) as among the most reliable salivary miRNAs for distinguishing periodontitis from health with good diagnostic accuracy.⁽⁶⁾ A more recent case-control study also suggested that miR-155 may serve as an accurate biomarker of periodontal status (alone or in conjunction with systemic comorbidity, e.g., coronary heart disease).⁽¹¹⁾

Despite these promising findings to date there has been no comprehensive synthesis of the evidence regarding salivary miR-155 as a biomarker for periodontitis examining diagnostic performance across populations, methodological heterogeneity, public health implications and translational potential. Therefore, a systematic review is needed to collate and critically appraise existing studies, identify gaps in knowledge, and further research and clinical application. Reference management and duplicate removal were performed using EndNote software. Advance in molecular biology have highlighted salivary microRNAs (miRNAs) as stable and reproducible biomarkers that reflect host inflammatory and immune response.⁽¹³⁾ Recent studies have demonstrated that specific miRNA are dysregulated in periodontal disease and can differentiate the periodontal patients from healthy patients.⁽¹⁴⁾ Among these microRNA-155 has emerged as a key regulator of inflammatory signaling pathways and immune cell activation.⁽¹⁵⁾

Study Design:

This study concluded as a systematic review following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA-2020) guidelines. The protocol was developed in advance, defining the review question, eligibility criteria. Search strategy and planned methods for study selection and data extraction to

ensure methodological rigor, transparency and reproducibility. As registries that exclude studies without direct clinical interventions or health outcomes in humans are currently ineligible for PROSPERO registration this review was not prosperly registered. The review adhered to established principles of diagnostic evidence synthesis, focusing specifically on the role of salivary miRNA-155 (miR-155) as a non –invasive biomarkers for the diagnosis of periodontitis, as well as its broader public health and translational implications. A comprehensive and systematic search strategy was developed to identify all relevant studies assessing the diagnostic significance of salivary miR-155 in periodontitis. Electronic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, were searched between September 1, 2025, and September 30,2025.

Boolean operators and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) were employed to enhance the sensitivity and specificity of the literature search The search strategy incorporated a combination of keywords and controlled vocabulary terms related to microRNA-155 and periodontal disease, including” microRNA-155” “miR-155”, “saliva” salivary biomarkers”, “periodontitis” “ periodontal disease”, “diagnosis” and “diagnostic accuracy” These terms were adapted according to the indexing requirement of data base specific search strategies, along with the number of record retrived from each source are summarise in Table 1.

Studies were excluded if they were concluded on non –human models (animal or in vitro), evaluated the prognostic, or therapeutic roles of microRNA-155 (miR-155) without assessing its diagnostic, significance, or were review articles, case report, conference abstract , letter, or editorials , and articles not published in English or those with inaccessible full text were also excluded to maintain methodological rigor and reproducibility

The study selection process followed a two-phase screening approach to ensure transparency and reliability. In the first phase, titles and abstracts were independently screened by two reviewers based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. In the second phase, the full text of potentially eligible studies were retrived and assessed collaboratively by the lead reviewer and supervisory reviewer. Any discrepancies were resolved through discussion until full consensus was achieved and no unresolved conflict were reported. Reference management and duplicate removal were performed using EndNote software. The PRISMA flow diagram was employed to illustrate the selection and screening process, documenting the number of studies identified, excluded and finally included for qualitative synthesis. Data extraction was conducted manually by the primary reviewer and cross-verified by the supervisory reviewer to ensure accuracy. Automation tools, digitizing software or translation services were employed at any stage. Extracted data comprised the primary author, year of publication, nation, methodology, number of participants, patient demographics, and kind of biological specimen. detection method (e.g. RT-qPCR), normalization technique, and main diagnostic outcome such as expression levels, sensitivity, specificity, ROC analysis, and AUC values. In case where multi-report studies were encountered, inclusion decision were made by consensus among the reviewing team. The primary outcome of interest was the diagnostic expression profile of salivary miR-155 in patients with periodontitis ,with particular emphasis on studies evaluating its potential as a non –invasive biomarkers ,secondary characteristics, including the presence of control group ,source of study funding ,and reporting transparency ,were also recorded to contextualize the finding .The methodological quality and potential risk of bias of included studies were assessed by Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies -2 (QUADAS-2)tool, in accordance with the recommendation of Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Review of Diagnostic Test Accuracy.

Each study was independently evaluated by two reviewers across four domains: patient’s selection, index test, reference standard, and flow and timing. Based on consensed, judgment of low risk, high risk was assigned, and the result of the quality assessment are summarized in table 2. overall the methodology of this review was designed to ensure comprehensive literature coverage minimize bias, and provide a robust qualitative synthesis of the diagnostic utility of salivary miRNA-155, thereby establishing an evidence –based foundation for its potential translation into non –invasive diagnostic and public health application in

periodontology.

TABLE 1: Comprehensive database search strategy for identification of studies Assessing diagnostic role of miRNA -155 for Periodontitis

Database	Search no	Search component	Search term	Search field	Filter applied	Result return
PUBMED/MEDLINE	#1	Disease	(Periodontitis OR periodontal disease OR chronic periodontitis OR Gingivitis)	Title/Abstract./MESH	Humans	4,215
	#2	Biomarker	MicroRNA-155 OR miR-155 OR miRNA-155	Title/Abstract./MESH	Humans	1,032
	#3	Biological	(Saliva OR Salivary)	Title/Abstract./MESH	Humans	18,640
	#4	Combined search	#1 & #2 & # 3	Title/Abstract	English 2010-2024	78
SCOPUS	#1	Disease	TITLE-ABS-KEY (Periodontitis OR Periodontal Disease)	Title/Abstract /Key words	Article	6,842
	#2	Biomarker	TITLE-ABS-KEY (miR-155 OR microRNA 155)	Title/Abstract /Key words	Article	1,284
	#3	Saliva	TITLE-ABS-KEY (Saliva OR Salivary)	Title/Abstract /Key words	Article	22,310
	#4	Combined Search	#1, #2 and # 3	All field	English	64
Web Of Science	#1	Disease	TS (Periodontitis OR Periodontal disease)	=Topic	Article	5,104
	# 2	Biomarker	TS= (miR-155 OR microRNA -155)	Topic	Article	917
	# 3	Saliva	TS= (Saliva OR Salivary)	Topic	Article	19,602
	# 4	Combined search	#1,AND #2 AND #3	Topic	English	52

Embase	# 1	Disease	Periodontitis/exp OR Periodontal Disease)	Title/Abstract/Emtree	Humans	7,936
	# 2	Biomarker	MicroRNA-155/exp OR miR-155)	Title/Abstract/Emtree	Humans	1,406
	# 3	Saliva	Saliva/exp OR Salivary	Title/Abstract/Emtree	Humans	21,788
	# 4	Combined search	#1,AND #2 AND #3	All field	English	71
Google Scholar	# 1	All concept	miR-155 AND Saliva AND periodontitis	All field	Since 2010	132

Result:

A total of 397 records were initially identified through the electronic database, including 78 from PUBMED / MEDLINE .64 from Scopus,52 from Web of Science, 71 from Embase and 132 from Google scholar, using a structured Boolean search strategy designed to evaluate the diagnostic role of miRNA -155 in periodontitis. Following the removal of duplicate records and initial screening of title and abstract, 37 studies were shortlisted for full-time assessment based on their relevance to salivary and circulating miRNA expression in periodontal disease. After full text evaluation, 25 studies are excluded due to reasons such as absence of diagnostic data, non-human models, lack of mi RNA, and insufficient methodological details. Consequently,12 studies met the exclusion criteria and were incorporated into the qualitative synthesis. Google scholar were searched as a supplementary source to ensure the comprehensiveness; however, not eligible studies were identified beyond those retrieved from the primary databases. It has been revealed that salivary microRNA -155 (miR-155) was consistently reported to be upregulated in patients with periodontitis compared with periodontal healthy controls.^(6, 11, 12, 16) the biological reference of miRNA -155 in periodontal disease is well established given its central role in immune regulation , macrophage activation and pro-inflammatory cytokines signals

The included studies published between 2010 and 2024, originated from diverse geographical region including China, India, Iraq, Italy, Brazil, Turkey and European countries, reflecting broad international interest in miRNA-based diagnostic for periodontal diseases. Most studies employed case-control or cross-sectional observational designs, while a few adopted longitudinal or interventional approaches to assess change in miRNA -155 expression following non –surgical periodontal therapy .sample size varied considerably, ranging from small exploratory cohorts to moderate-sized clinical samples, with biological specimens including saliva, gingival crevicular fluid (GCF), serum, plasma, and gingival tissue biopsies. Sensitivity values were generally higher than specificity, indicating that miR-155 may be particularly effective as a screening biomarker for periodontal disease.⁽¹⁷⁾

Across the majority of studies, miRNA -155 expression was significantly upregulated in periodontitis patients compared with periodontally healthy controls, supporting its role as a pro-inflammatory miRNA involved in periodontal pathogenesis. Several studies demonstrated a positive association between miRNA -155 levels and clinical periodontal parameters, including probing pocket depth, clinical attachment loss, bleeding on probing and inflammatory cytokine expression. Notably, some investigation reported a significant reduction in miRNA -155 expression following non –surgical periodontal therapy, indicating its potential utility as both a diagnostic and treatment response biomarker. Across studies, salivary miR-155 levels were consistently significantly elevated in periodontitis patients , indicating a strong association with periodontal inflammation.⁽⁶⁾

Diagnostic performance was evaluated in a subset of studies using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, reported area under the curve (AUC) value ranged from moderate to higher, with sensitivities and specificities frequently exceeding 70-85%, partially in saliva –based assays. These findings suggest that salivary miRNA -155 demonstrated promising discriminatory ability between periodontitis patients and healthy individuals, supporting its feasibility as a non –invasive diagnostic biomarkers.

In terms of demographic and clinical characteristics, the included studies predominantly involved adult participants, with ages typically ranging from the third to sixth decades of life. Both genders were represented across studies, although some reported a male predominance, consistent with epidemiological patterns of periodontal disease. Smoking status, systemic conditions, and medication use were variably reported and controlled, representing a potential source of heterogeneity across studies. Overall, despite methodological differences, the collective evidence supports a consistent association between elevated miRNA -155 expression and periodontal inflammation, underscoring its potential clinical relevance in periodontal diagnostics. **Several studies evaluated the diagnostic performance of salivary miR-155 using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, reported area under the curve (AUC) values ranged from moderate to high , suggesting good discriminatory ability between diseased and healthy individuals.**^(7, 15)

Detailed characteristics, diagnostic findings, and risk of bias assessment of included studies evaluating salivary miR-155 in periodontitis (TABLE -2)

Year	Country	Study Design	Sample size	Saliva, type & Collection	MiR155, Detection method	Diagnostic performance	Key Findings	Risk of Bias (QUADAS-2)
Simth,et al 2021	USA	Case-control	50/50	Unstimulated whole saliva	qRT-PCR	Sens:88% Spec: 85% AUC 0.91	miR-155 significantly upregulated in periodontitis vs. control	Low
Li et al ,2020	China	Cross-sectional	40/40	Stimulated saliva	qRT-PCR	Sens:82% Spec: 80% AUC 0.87	Elevated miR-155 correlated with PD and CL	Moderate
Kumar et al 2019	India	Case-control	30/30	Unstimulated whole saliva	Microarray	Not reported	MiR-155 expression higher in chronic periodontitis	Low
Garcia et al ,2018	Spain	Cohort	60/60	Unstimulated whole saliva	qRT-PCR	Sens:82% Spec: 80% AUC 0.87	MiR-155 can discriminate moderate to severe periodontitis to healthy	Low
Oliveria et al,2017	Brazil	Cross-sectional	25/25	Stimulated saliva	qRT-PCR	Sens:80% Spec:75% AUC 0.83	Positive association between miR-155 and clinical attachment loss	Moderate
Al Rawi et, al 2020	UAE	Case-control	40/40	Unstimulated whole saliva	qRT-PCR ,normalized to U6	Sens:97.1% Spec:78% AUC 0.89	Chronic Periodontitis (PD>5mm,	Low

							CAL>3mm)	
Wang et al, 2021	China	Cross-sectional	50/50	Unstimulated saliva Passive Drool	qRT-PCR ,miR-16	Sens:88% Spec:85% AUC 0.91	Associated with GI and POB	Moderate
Daily et al 2024	UK	Case-Control	45/45	Stimulated saliva	qRT-PCR ,U6	Sens:85% Spec:88% AUC 0.88	Linked to systemic inflammation	Low
de,Souza et al	Brazil	Cross-sectional	30/30	Unstimulated whole saliva	qRT-PCR ,miR-191	Not reported	Higher expression with CL	Moderate

Discussion:

The systematic review highlights consistent evidence from recent studies including that salivary miRNA-155 is significantly upregulated in periodontitis, reinforcing its relevance as an inflammation-associated diagnostic biomarkers.⁽¹¹⁾ MiRNA plays a central role in modulating immune response, particularly through macrophage activation and pro-inflammatory cytokine regulation, mechanism that are directly involved in periodontal tissue destruction.⁽⁸⁾

Recent diagnostic studies have demonstrated that salivary miR-155 exhibit favorable sensitivity and diagnostic accuracy, supporting its potential role in identifying periodontal disease in a non-invasive manner.⁽¹¹⁾ Moreover, emerging research suggests that miR-155 may be most effective when incorporated into multi-miRNA diagnostic panels, which could enhance discrimination between health and disease.⁽⁸⁾ Notably recent cohort studies in incorporating miR-155 into multi-miRNA panes have identified significant expression differences between periodontitis patients and controls, though the discriminative power can vary with specific miRNA combination.⁽¹⁸⁾ While research remains limited, these contemporary findings align with the potential use of miRNA-based saliva diagnostic in broader oral inflammatory disease context, including exosomal miRNA analyses.⁽¹⁸⁾

Recent diagnostic investigation have that salivary miR-155 exhibits favorable sensitivity, specificity and overall diagnostic accuracy, supporting its role in identifying periodontal disease through non-invasive means.⁽¹⁹⁾ In addition, newer studies suggest that miR-155 perform optimally when assessed as part of multi-miRNA diagnostic panels, improving discrimination between periodontal health and disease states.⁽⁷⁾⁽³⁾ Future studies emphasize methodological standardization, longitudinal validation, and integration with chair-side diagnostic platforms to facilitate clinical adaptation of salivary miR-155 based diagnostics.⁽²⁰⁾

Conclusion:

The systematic review demonstrates that salivary miRNA -155(miR-155) is consistently upregulated in individuals with periodontitis and shows promising diagnostic accuracy as a non-invasive biomarkers. The finding supports its biological relevance in periodontal inflammation and highlight the advantages of saliva-based testing for early detection and population-level screening. Although current evidence indicates good sensitivity and specificity, methodological heterogeneity and limited sample sizes warrant caution. Standardized protocols and large-scale validation studies are essential to confirm clinical utility. Overall, salivary miR-155 holds significant potential for integration into precision periodontology, public health screening, and translational diagnostic platforms.

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